

Synthesis, spectral characterization and electrochemical behavior of some cobalt(III) complexes of the type $cis\text{-}\beta\text{-}[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{RC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$

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Abstract : Seven new cobalt(III) complexes of the type $cis\text{-}\beta\text{-}[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{RC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$, where R = H, *p*-Me, *p*-OMe, *p*-Et, *p*-OEt, *p*-F and *m*-Me have been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, UV-Vis, FT-IR and ^1H NMR spectral techniques. The results of the spectral studies reveal that these complexes possess a $cis\text{-}\beta$ arrangement of ligands around the cobalt ion. Molar conductance measurements support the 1 : 2 natures of these complexes. TGA and DTA studies reveal that these complexes are thermally stable up to 175 °C. Cyclic voltammetric studies of these complexes and a fairly linear correlation ($r = 0.93$) of reduction potential data with the Hammett's substituent constants indicates that the electroreduction depends on the nature of the sixth ligand.

Keywords : Cobalt(III) complexes, substituted anilines, electrochemical and spectral studies.

Introduction

The role of metal complexes in biological system is of paramount importance. The development of bio-inorganic chemistry has followed the initial route of studies on low molecular weight metal compounds as active site models of metallo-proteins. Such biomimetic studies have helped in understanding their structural and electronic properties and the role of protein in environment on the biochemical function of the metal prosthetic group. Model studies in search of the mechanisms for the enzymatic reactions catalyzed by coenzyme B₁₂ and methylcobalamin (methyl B₁₂), the only known organocobalt compounds of nature, exceeded this objective and has become a general contribution to coordination chemistry¹.

The enormous strides made during the past through the cobalt(III) compounds of the credible cobaloxime and Costa-type models provide valuable insight into the elegant chemistry orchestrated by the primary bio-inorganic system. Nevertheless, the related chemistry of the cobalt complexes is intriguing and informative transition metal chemistry²⁻⁷. Therefore, the synthesis and physicochemical studies of cobalt(III) complexes would be of significance to shed some light into the mechanism of biologically important processes. Having the above mentioned background in our mind, we report, in this article, the synthesis, spectral characterization and electrochemical properties of some cobalt(III) complexes. Although the

synthesis and kinetics of base hydrolysis of $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{amine})\text{Cl}]^+$ type complexes with aliphatic and aromatic amines as ligand has been reported earlier⁸, this the first attempt to prepare and characterize cobalt(III) complexes with substituted anilines as one of the ligands along with trien and chloride ion. Such an attempt will definitely help to study the structural effects, in general, and nature of the sixth ligand, in particular, on the reactivity/properties of these type of complexes.

Experimental

Materials : All chemicals used were of commercially available reagent grade. Triethylenetetramine (trien) was distilled before use. Substituted anilines used were purchased from Aldrich and were used as received. Double distilled water was used for recording cyclic voltammograms and conductance measurements.

Physical measurements and methods : FT-IR spectra were recorded using KBr disc on JASCO FT-IR 460 Plus spectrometer. The electronic absorption spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu (UV 240, Graphicord) double beam spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched quartz cells. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded at Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai. Elemental analysis for CHN and TGA and DTA were recorded at the Central Electrochemical Research Institute, Karaikudi. Conductance measurements were performed using an Elico, India conductivity bridge. Magnetic measurements were carried out at Indian Insti-

tute of Technology, Chennai.

All electrochemical experiments were performed at 25 °C using a standard three-electrode, two compartment configuration with a glassy carbon (GC-3 mm) working electrode, a spiral platinum counter electrode and a Ag|AgCl (KCl sat.) reference electrode. The carbon electrodes were polished between experiments with alumina (0.5 µm) paste. The cyclic voltammetric experiments were carried out with a computer-controlled electrochemical system (CHI643B Electrochemical Analyzer) at 50 mV s⁻¹. Solutions of electrolyte, cobalt(III)-complexes, were prepared with double distilled water. All solutions were deoxygenated thoroughly by purging with nitrogen gas for 15–20 min before commencement of the measurement.

Synthesis of cobalt(III) complexes : The cobalt(III) complexes of the type [Co(trien)(RC₆H₄NH₂)Cl]Cl₂ (where R = H, *p*-Me, *p*-OMe, *p*-Et, *p*-OEt, *p*-F and *m*-Me) were prepared from [Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl⁹. In a typical experiment, acid free [Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl (3.2 mmol) was suspended in water (2 ml) and was ground in a mortar with dropwise addition of the R-aniline (3.2 mmol) for nearly 0.5–2 h. Calculated amounts of liquid of substituted anilines were added directly while solid anilines were dissolved in 2 ml alcohol and added. After the addition was completed, the mixture was set aside (~0.5 h) until no further change in colour was noticed. The resultant paste was rinsed with

alcohol and ether over a Buckner funnel and was recrystallized twice in acetone-DMF mixture.

Results and discussion

The analytical and physical data of the cobalt(III) complexes of the type [Co(trien)(RC₆H₄NH₂)Cl]Cl₂ (where R = H, *p*-Me, *p*-OMe, *p*-Et, *p*-OEt, *p*-F and *m*-Me) are given in Table 1. All the complexes are intensely coloured. All the cobalt(III) complexes gave satisfactory CHN analysis confirming to the general composition. The complexes are all diamagnetic as expected. The molar conductance values (Table 1) in water (298 K) identify the species as 1 : 2 electrolytes¹⁰.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectra of the cobalt(III) complexes were recorded in water in the 700–210 nm region. The absorption maxima and molar extinction coefficients are listed in Table 2. A representa-

Table 2. Electronic spectral data for the cobalt(III) complexes

R ^a	¹ A _g → ¹ T _{1g} nm (log ε) ^a	Charge transfer nm (log ε) ^b
None	494 (2.5)	353 (2.4)
<i>p</i> -Me	494 (2.4)	350 (2.3)
<i>p</i> -OMe	461 (2.8)	357 (2.8)
<i>p</i> -Et	494 (2.3)	354 (2.3)
<i>p</i> -OEt	460 (3.1)	331 (3.1)
<i>p</i> -F	493 (2.3)	354 (2.3)
<i>m</i> -Me	494 (2.4)	351 (2.2)

^aSubstituent in the aniline moiety.

^bε_{max} in M⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Table 1. Colour, elemental analyses and molar conductance of the cobalt(III) complexes

R ^a	Colour	Elemental analyses (%) :			Molar conductance (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)
		Found	Calcd.)		
		C	H	N	
None	Brown	35.46 (35.73)	5.97 (5.95)	16.32 (17.37)	137
<i>p</i> -Me	Pink	36.82 (37.41)	6.29 (6.47)	16.60 (16.79)	123
<i>p</i> -OMe	Brown	35.53 (36.03)	6.36 (6.24)	16.46 (16.17)	130
<i>p</i> -Et	Purple	37.83 (38.98)	6.68 (6.73)	16.05 (16.24)	104
<i>p</i> -OEt	Brown	37.06 (37.58)	6.47 (6.48)	15.13 (15.66)	111
<i>p</i> -F	Brown	34.31 (34.20)	5.59 (5.70)	16.22 (16.63)	140
<i>m</i> -Me	Purple	36.84 (37.41)	6.40 (6.47)	15.64 (16.79)	124

^aSubstituents in the aniline moiety.

tive electronic spectrum of [Co(trien)(RC₆H₄NH₂)Cl]Cl₂ is shown in Fig. 1. Regular octahedral Co^{III}L₆³⁺ complexes have two UV-Vis spin allowed transitions, ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g}. In tetragonal complexes of the type Co^{III}L₄X₂, the first band is split into two, ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g at low energy and ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} at higher energy. In *trans* complexes this splitting is sufficient to completely resolve this band into two components, this is rarely the case in *cis* complexes. Further, ε in *cis* complexes are much greater than the corresponding *trans* values¹¹. In the present study, all the cobalt(III) complexes show two absorption bands. The absorption bands at ca. 350 nm of the complexes were assigned to the metal to ligand charge transfer band, while the bands at ca. 490 nm were assigned to the first absorption band i.e. due to ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} transition. The observed positions and intensities strongly suggest a *cis* rather than a *trans* structure¹¹. Further, the electronic spectrum of these complexes were

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ in aqueous solution.

found to resemble that for $\text{cis-}\beta\text{-Co}(\text{trien})\text{Cl}_2^+$ ion suggesting that these complexes may also possess a $\text{cis-}\beta$ arrangement of ligands around the cobalt ion¹². Furthermore, the positions of these bands vary very little through the series of complexes, thus indicating that the ligand field about the cobalt ion remains almost constant.

Infrared spectra : Buckingham and Jones¹³ suggested that infrared spectra are useful to distinguish geometrical isomers of some trien complexes. Only those FT-IR bands characteristic of these complexes are considered and they are presented in Table 3. In all the cobalt(III) complexes studied the N-H stretching region occurs in the range of $3006\text{--}3330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is characteristic of $\text{cis-}\beta$ -isomer ($2985\text{--}3330\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The bands $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to the anti-symmetric NH_2 bending vibrations. It is well established that the peaks in the $1290\text{--}1335\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region

is due to the symmetric NH_2 deformation. Further, these bands remain unaltered neither by the variation in the anion nor by substitution in the coordination sphere^{13,14}. Thus, in the present study, the bands due to NH_2 deformation observed in the $1281\text{--}1309\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region confirm that the structure of the cobalt(III) complexes is similar to that of $\text{cis-}\beta\text{-}[\text{Co}(\text{trien})\text{X}_2]^{2+}$ ion proposed earlier¹³.

By a comparison with the assignments of Buckingham and Jones¹³ for the vibrations of the trien chelate ring the bands in the $1428\text{--}1491$, $1250\text{--}1304$ and $867\text{--}908\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions are assigned to CH_2 bending, wagging and rocking respectively. In the FT-IR spectra of the cobalt(III) complexes a new band observed in the $544\text{--}572\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region may be attributed to the M-N stretching¹⁴.

^1H NMR spectra : The ^1H NMR spectra of the complexes were recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ as solvent. All other complexes under investigation show similar patterns in the ^1H NMR spectrum in addition to the characteristic signals corresponding to the substituent in the aniline moiety. It is evident from the spectra that the following two important general regions were present in all the cobalt(III) complexes. (i) A signal centered at approximately 3.33 ppm belongs to the center ethylene linkage of the trien ligand. The remaining center ring protons, as well as the protons in the terminal ethylene linkages, may overlap to form the complex multiplet centered at approximately 2.88 ppm . Parallel observations have been made in the ^1H NMR spectra of Co^{III} complexes containing trien ligand^{15,16}. Toyota and Yamamoto¹⁶ have successfully employed ^1H NMR spectroscopy to distinguish the $\text{cis-}\alpha$ and $\text{cis-}\beta$ isomers of $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{A})]\text{Cl}_2$ type complexes and obtained characteristic signals around 2.88 ppm . In the present study identical signals confirm that the cobalt(III) complexes under investigation exist as $\text{cis-}\beta$ isomers rather than $\text{cis-}\alpha$ ones. (ii) The resonance peaks

Table 3. FT-IR spectral data of the cobalt(III) complexes^a

R^b	N-H stretching	NH_2 bending	NH_2 deformation	CH_2 bending	CH_2 wagging	CH_2 rocking	M-N stretching
None	3079m	1599s	1281m	1491s	1281m	874m	549m
<i>p</i> -Me	3107s	1607sh	1309m	1436s	1278w	873m	547s
<i>p</i> -OMe	3006w	1648m	1309m	1450m	1250m	867w	551s
<i>p</i> -Et	3114b	1654s	1307m	1431s	1268w	876m	572s
<i>p</i> -OEt	3298m	1613m	1306m	1451w	1256m	872w	550s
<i>p</i> -F	3330s	1581s	1308w	1433m	1300w	867m	544s
<i>m</i> -Me	3113m	1593s	1299w	1428s	1304w	908w	568m

^aIn cm^{-1} .

^bSubstituent in the aniline moiety.

in the 6.2–7.2 ppm range may be assigned to the protons in the benzene ring¹⁷.

The downfield shift occurs with the NH₂ protons (aniline moiety) appearing at 5.68 ppm in the ¹H NMR spectrum of the [Co(trien)(C₆H₅NH₂)Cl]Cl₂ complex, corresponding to 5.1 ppm in the free ligand¹⁸ as expected due to coordination of the aniline nitrogen to the metal ion.

Thermal analysis : Thermal investigation of a representative complex, [Co(trien)(C₆H₅NH₂)Cl]Cl₂, was made in the temperature interval from room temperature to 1000 °C in stream of nitrogen. The TGA curve obtained at 20 °C min⁻¹ heating rate and corresponding DTA curve are shown in Fig. 2. Results of the thermogravimetric analysis and DTA peaks are presented in Table 4. It is evident from the figure that the cobalt(III) complex de-

Fig. 2. TGA and DTA curves of [Co(trien)(C₆H₅NH₂)Cl]Cl₂.

composes in a four stage process as shown by the presence of four breaks in the TGA graph and the presence of a corresponding number of peaks in the DTA graph¹⁹. The complex was found to be thermally stable up to 175 °C as the TGA plateau shows barring the removal of moisture from the complex. Above 175 °C a rapid decomposition occurs with a mass loss corresponding to the loss

of two chlorine atoms present outside the coordination sphere (Stage I). The first stage ends at around 211 °C. The sequential occurrence of stages II and III are better visualized on the DTA curve which has the twin peak appearing serially. The loss of masses of about 29% and 5% for stages II and III respectively are recorded and are accounted by the loss of trien ligand in two stages. The procedural decomposition temperature for stage IV is close to 522 °C and the decomposition ends at 630 °C. Mass loss of 25% accounts for the loss of the aniline moiety into volatile matter leaving the final residue. The DTA peak indicates that the process is of single stage.

Electrochemical studies : Cyclic voltammetric behaviour of Co^{III} complexes were examined in water containing sodium perchlorate (0.1 M) as supporting electrolyte at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. The redox potential data for all the complexes in water is given in Table 5. Cyclic voltammograms of all these complexes exhibited one well-defined redox peak corresponding to the Co^{III}/Co^{II} couple. Similar observations were also made by Vasilevkiš *et al.*²⁰ and Berthaortiz *et al.*²¹ for cobalt(III) complexes. An irreversible cathodic peak is observed for all the complexes at negative potentials, which may be probably due to the reduction of Co^{II} to Co^I. On the positive side an irreversible oxidation corresponding to Co^{III} to Co^{IV} was observed around 0.8 to 0.9 V²². The ΔE_p values (Table 5) show the reversible (H, *m*-Me and *p*-F) and quasi-reversible (*p*-OMe, *p*-OEt, *p*-Me and *p*-Et) nature of Co^{III}/Co^{II} redox couple⁶.

The anodic and cathodic potential data indicate the sensitivity of the Co^{III} complexes to the nature of the sixth ligand. Similar phenomenon is described in the electrochemistry of cobaloximes²³. The ratio (R_{Ip}) of the anodic peak current to the cathodic peak current is close to unity (0.8 < R_{Ip} < 1) which again indicates the

Table 4. Summary of TGA and DTA studies of [Co(trien)(C₆H₅NH₂)Cl]Cl₂

Stages	TGA Temp. range (°C)	DTA Peak temp. (°C)	Mass loss (%)		Probable leaving group
			Exp.	Calcd.	
I	174–211	193	15	17	2Cl
II	211–396	301	29	31	0.85 trien
III	396–521	428	5	5	0.15 trien
IV	521–630	574	25	23	Aniline

Table 5. Electrochemical data (E_p, V) from CV for the cobalt(III) complexes in water

R ^a	E _{pa} (III/IV)	E _{pc} (II/I)	E _{pc} (III/II)	E _{pa} (II/III)	ΔE _p	E _{1/2}
H	0.923	-0.218	0.288	0.270	18	0.279
<i>p</i> -Me	0.860	-0.360	-0.192	-0.308	116	-0.250
<i>p</i> -OMe	0.864	-0.392	-0.198	-0.344	146	-0.271
<i>p</i> -Et	0.852	-0.342	-0.195	-0.125	70	-0.160
<i>p</i> -OEt	0.861	-0.365	-0.213	-0.316	103	-0.265
<i>p</i> -F	0.820	-0.092	0.254	0.229	25	0.242
<i>m</i> -Me	0.834	-0.330	0.220	0.193	27	0.207

^aSubstituents in the aniline moiety.

reversibility or quasi-reversibility of the $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ couple. Further, the ratio is independent of the scan rate. It was also found that the peak currents were essentially constant for several cycles. These results indicate that there were no chemical reactions coupled with the electron transfer²⁴. Furthermore, the reduction potential E_{pc} was found to be dependent on scan rate. The correlation of log scan rate versus E_{pc} was found to be linear ($r = 0.986$, $sd = 0.006$). The rate of reduction computed from the slope of the straight line for $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(p\text{-FC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ in water was found to be 0.2554 s^{-1} .

The effect of substituents in aniline moiety on the redox potentials of $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ couple was studied with seven substituted anilines as ligands in water. The $E_{1/2}$ correlates linearly with the Hammett's substituent constants²⁵ ($r = 0.93$, $sd = 0.10$, $\rho = 1.977 \pm 0.35$) and a typical plot is shown in Fig. 3. Positive value of the reaction constant, ρ indicate that electron donating substituents shift the redox reaction to a more cathodic potential⁶. The reaction constants for metal reductions are always smaller when compared to simple ligands as observed herein²⁷.

Fig. 3. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ versus Hammett's substituent constant, σ in water.

Conclusion : Based on the foregoing spectral features, the following structure has been proposed for the $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{RC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)\text{Cl}]^{2+}$ ions with *cis*- β configuration. The electrochemical behaviour of these complexes was found to be dependent on the nature of the sixth ligand.

$L = \text{RC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$ (where $R = \text{H}, p\text{-Me}, p\text{-OMe}, p\text{-Et}, p\text{-OEt}, p\text{-F}$ and $m\text{-Me}$)

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